

SATELLITE REMOTE SENSING AND OCEAN PHYSICS

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Existing and prospective satellite ocean remote sensing systems, and data sets from previous systems, are reviewed in the context of their contributions to solving priority scientific problems in physical oceanography. The role of altimeters, scatterometers, microwave radiometers, synthetic aperture radars, (SAR), infrared imagery, and color imagery in determining the surface dynamic topography, surface winds and waves, sea surface temperature, tides, sea ice, and upper ocean optical properties is considered, as is the use of this information for the estimation of the mean and transient circulation of the ocean, including oceanic eddies and fronts. Satellite remote sensing measurements of the ocean will be most useful when used together with modern in situ measurements as complementary components in a real-time global observational network for the purposes of operational ocean prediction as well as for basic research on climate-related and transient ocean circulation modeling topics. Because of the enormous volume of data involved, and the complexity of the algorithms required to process it, data processing facilities, data base management, and data exchange issues loom large. A new era in synoptic and quantitative physical oceanography will commence later in the decade with the launch and validation of the planned satellites, especially in their application to the World Ocean Circulation Experiment (WOCE) and operational ocean prediction.

Priority Scientific Problems in Physical Oceanography

Physical Oceanography

Physical oceanography, or ocean physics, is concerned with understanding the ocean as a physical system, as both a dynamical and a thermodynamical fluid system. This system encompasses not only the interior of the ocean but also the interaction of the ocean with the atmosphere, sea floor, cryosphere, and the continents. In the broadest sense, ocean physics also incorporates the transmission of acoustic, optical, and other electromagnetic energy forms with the ocean's boundaries.

Ocean Variability

To obtain a predictive knowledge of the physical state of the ocean, it is necessary to understand, observe, and model ocean variability on a host of space and time scales. The ocean has climatic and weather variability much as the atmosphere does, and it is much influenced by such variations in the atmosphere. Whereas atmospheric synoptic scale eddies have spatial scales of ca. 1,000 km, oceanic eddies have spatial scales of ca. 100 km. Thus, the ocean has ca. 100 times as many "storm centers" as the atmosphere at any one time and needs an order-of-magnitude more dense observing system. However, there is a compensation: since oceanic eddies propagate at one thousandth the speed of atmospheric eddies, and exist a hundred times as long, the oceanic propagation (and duration) time scale is one hundred times that of the atmosphere. Hence, corresponding to a typical atmospheric synoptic time scale of a week, the typical oceanic synoptic mesoscale time scale is a year or two. Similar logic applies to oceanic jets (intense currents), their meanders, and fronts in relation to atmospheric jets, their meanders, and fronts. Therefore, the high tem-

poral and modest spatial sampling rates required for observing atmospheric weather can be traded for high spatial and modest temporal sampling rates for observing oceanic weather. The high sampling rates of 10 to 20 km required to resolve ocean weather features is the source of the oceanographer's dilemma. With conventional measurements, the oceanographer is confined to studying ocean weather in only a regional domain and along shipping lanes or studying ocean climate on a very large scale, hoping to average-out the shorter term, and presumed smaller amplitude, fluctuations due to ocean weather, and ignoring the influence of ocean weather on ocean climate. Such a situation is unsatisfactory.

The Working Assumption

In the physical oceanographer's interest in satellite ocean remote sensing there is an implicit assumption: the dominant oceanic processes will have sufficient, comprehensible surface manifestations that an enormous increase in remotely sensed surface information will allow inference of the physical (mass and flow) structure throughout the water column. This assumption may seem unsound. However, the physical oceanographer is equipped with some a priori knowledge from climatology, oceanic process studies and models, and ocean dynamical principles to aid in the task.

Other Topics

Of course there are scientific problem areas beyond ocean weather and climate of concern to the physical oceanographer. For example, though relatively well understood, there remains much to be done to predict satisfactorily ocean tides and wind waves and swell.

The sea ice boundaries of the polar regions fluctuate greatly with the seasons, and on time scales of years and longer. The position of the ice edge is an important determinant in air-sea heat and other exchanges at high latitudes, and, thus, influences the atmospheric and oceanic climates. The ice edge per se is a complex region of detached ice floes and vigorous oceanic eddies and fronts, and associated intense oceanic mixing. This marginal ice zone (MIZ) is an air-sea-ice boundary region under the influence of mesoscale processes which are just now beginning to be understood. Of course, the physical processes controlling the temporal and spatial variability of the ice cover and leads, and of the mass and circulation fields in the Arctic Ocean per se, are of increasing scientific and operational interest.

The variable transfers of heat, moisture, and momentum between the atmosphere and ocean strongly influence the mass and circulation fields of the upper 100m or so of the ocean. An appreciable predictive capability for the response of the upper ocean thermal structure to atmospheric forcing is rapidly emerging. This capability has immediate applications to fisheries and climate studies.

Application of Satellite Remote Sensing to Priority Problems in Physical Oceanography

Mesoscale Ocean Variability

At the present time, satellite IR and CZCS imagery can be useful in locating and characterizing some synoptic/mesoscale oceanic eddies, fronts, and meandering currents. As demonstrated by SEASAT, more satisfactory quantitative information on the dynamic topography associated with mesoscale ocean features can be obtained from satellite radar altimeters. Since variable surface winds influence the evolution of these features, improved estimates of the surface wind velocities from scatterometers should be useful for the prediction of mesoscale variability. SAR can also play a role akin to IR and color imagery in location and characterization, due to the modulation of surface and internal gravity wave fields by mesoscale currents.

Ocean Tides and Wind Waves and Swell

As demonstrated by SEASAT, the radar altimeter can return surface height information of sufficient quality to analyze the open ocean tidal height field. It also provides information on significant wave heights and surface wind speed, from which swell can be determined, too. Of course, scatterometer surface wind velocities can be useful for predicting wind waves and swell.

Sea Ice Boundaries

Passive microwave radiometers respond to the discontinuity in emissivity in crossing from sea to ice in the MIZ. Thus, they are effective in delineating the position of the ice edge. SAR is also useful in imaging the variable ice structure in the MIZ. Scatterometer winds will be useful in predicting the ice pack movement of the MIZ.

Air-Sea Interaction

Determination of the exchange between the atmosphere and ocean will benefit from scatterometer surface winds, multichannel IR radiometers which can determine SST accurately, and atmospheric sounders which can estimate nearsurface air temperature and moisture. With the air-sea exchange forcing functions well-determined, upper ocean thermal structure forecasting should improve.

Data Base Management

General

The enormity of the satellite remote sensing data base acquired by SEASAT, and by the ongoing IR and color images, is a new experience for oceanographers, - one which stresses computational facilities and data distribution systems. Also, the complexity and uncertainty of the algorithms which must be applied to the acquired data to produce geophysical information dictate careful analysis, test, and evaluation procedures.

PODS

The Pilot Ocean Data System is a NASA-sponsored developmental data base management system under evolution at JPL. It is designed to process, archive, document, and distribute satellite remote sensing data of oceanographic interest. It supports algorithm evaluation efforts for the ocean science community. PODS also includes a system of remote, interactive user terminals for information retrieval and assessment purposes, which facilitates data distribution and

other facets of data utilization. It now allows access to almost all of the SEASAT data, with exception of SAR data. Thus, valuable experience is being gained for the effective utilization of ocean remote sensing data of the future.

World Ocean Circulation Experiment

WOCE is a grand enterprise by which the world physical oceanography community plans to determine the general circulation of the ocean over the course of several years, beginning at the end of this decade. Satellite altimeters and scatterometers will play a central role in this activity. WOCE will provide a solid basis for evaluating the ocean's role in the global climate, and it will stimulate the evolution of operational ocean prediction.

SUMMARY

Experience with the limited satellite data sets of the past and present suggests that the highly capable prospective satellite data sets which will be available several years from now may accelerate the scientific progress of physical oceanography, and its application to operational ocean prediction.